

REASONS FOR WEAK PERFORMANCE OF JUNIOR SCHOOL CHILDREN

Mingboeva Mokhina Tulkinjon kizi

student, Tashkent State pedagogical university named after Nizami, Uzbekistan, Tashkent

E-mail: mokhinamingboyeva20@gmail.com

Akhmedova Mahfuza Sadykovna

Scientific director. Associate Professor,

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami,

Uzbekistan, Tashkent

E-mail: maxfuzasadikovna@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11523574>

Abstract. *This article discusses the problem of underachievement of younger schoolchildren. Analysis of the concept of “underachieving child”. As well as the psychological characteristics of lagging students, their causes and ways to overcome this problem*

Keywords: *school failure, educational activities, reasons for failure, poor academic performance, teacher, family, psychologists, types of failure, the problem of school failure.*

ПРИЧИНЫ СЛАБОЙ УСПЕШНОСТИ МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается проблема неуспеваемости младших школьников. Анализ понятия «неуспевающий ребенок». А также психологические особенности отставания учащихся, их причины и пути преодоления данной проблемы.*

Ключевые слова: *школьная неуспеваемость, учебная деятельность, причины неуспеваемости, неуспеваемость, учитель, семья, психологи, виды неуспеваемости, проблема школьной неуспеваемости.*

Each teacher interacts with different categories of students in his activities. Some can boast of excellent memory and speed of assimilation of material. Others take much longer to absorb the information they receive to understand and put in more effort to achieve the desired grades. However, some students regularly experience learning difficulties. Difficulties in the educational process, especially those that arise in elementary school, significantly complicate students' assimilation of the school curriculum. It is during the initial period of learning that students lay the foundations of a knowledge system that is replenished in subsequent years, while at the same time mental and practical operations, behavior and skills are formed that make subsequent learning and practical activities impossible.

The lack of a foundation and failure to master initial knowledge and skills causes unjustified difficulties in mastering the secondary school curriculum and, as a result, they often fall behind in the learning process.

To do this, it is necessary to be able to identify possible causes of difficulties in educational activities, determine which causes are valid in a particular case, and eliminate them or modify the results.

The problem of school failure is complex and very important. They have been trying to solve this problem for a long time in different ways. Previously, one way was to repeat a student's grade and wait until he mastered the grade-specific curriculum.

Currently, there are special schools and equalization classes for these children, but their effectiveness is not always high.

The very fact of placing a student in such a school or class is shocking. Puts him in the lowest category. Therefore, it is necessary to find ways to increase the level of correctional work with such children in regular classes.

Pedagogical failure is understood as a discrepancy between students' preparation and the requirements for the content of education, which is recorded after a significant period of the educational process. This is a series of classes devoted to the study of one topic or section of a course, year, academic quarter, half-year.

Underachievement is associated with the personal characteristics of students, developmental conditions and genetic factors. To be effective in overcoming school failure, you must first identify the cause. In each specific case, the reasons are individual.

The failures of younger schoolchildren and all the difficulties associated with the educational process have always worried many psychologists and teachers. It is necessary to classify the reasons for the failure of younger schoolchildren.

Psychologists argue that there are common reasons that are characteristic of certain groups of schoolchildren. Teachers usually cite reluctance to learn, lack of cognitive interest, and negative influences from family and distance.

One of the most important internal reasons today is the health defects of children of primary school age, caused by a sharp deterioration in the level of material well-being of the family and low intellectual development.

Therefore, in the real life of a student, many reasons are intertwined, and the problem is not only a reluctance to learn, but is also much more complex than it seems at first glance.

Often the reasons for poor academic performance are unfavorable living conditions in the family, lack of control and support for adult learning, conflict within the family and lack of a daily routine.

Dysfunctional, single-parent families, lack of contact with parents, low financial level of the family, school environment, media distances. All these social factors can also lead to student failure.

Junior school age is a turning point in the development of personality; the child is faced with a new social environment. Therefore, during this period, teachers should pay more attention to students. Get rid of any problems that arise in a timely manner. Teachers must understand that there are no children who cannot do anything. All students can be taught, but everyone has their own path to progress. In most cases, teachers choose traditional methods. Work with low-achieving students - based on additional classes. Additional activities with children are not always effective because they are not suitable for all children. For example, if the child has cognitive problems or family problems. For the teacher's work to be effective, it is necessary to take into account the characteristics of each child.

The main goal of working with children is to teach them to think. Therefore, it is necessary to select materials for classes and extracurricular activities. This is how the child develops logical and creative thinking skills.

It is also worth noting the important role of primary school psychologists. The successful work of psychologists also requires complex interactions between families and classroom teachers. Because the main reasons for the academic lags of schoolchildren are family problems, children's fears and uncertainty. Psychologists work with families to better help a child overcome problems since the child spends most of his time with his family. The family plays a vital role in the comprehensive and harmonious development of children.

The main activity of younger schoolchildren is learning, therefore it is necessary to support and help younger schoolchildren and pay more attention to educational activities.

The relevance of this article lies in the fact that the poor performance of primary school students has a negative impact in secondary schools and other places. Therefore, the process of studying the problem, identifying it in a timely manner and taking action is currently very important. This is why the efforts of teachers, psychologists and families are so important.

All these methods of solving problems have a beneficial effect on the development of positive aspects of the personality: hard work, high performance, etc. These measures can

contribute to partial development of the personality and the emergence of faith in one's educational abilities.

REFERENCES

1. M. S. Akhmedova. Using multimedia and interaktiva technologies in teaching Russian to students. EPRA International Journal of Research und Development Volume: 5, Issue:3, March 2020/ ISSN:2455-7838
2. M. S. Akhmedova. "Advantages of using modern information and communication technologies in the educational process". "EASTERN EUROPEAN SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL" ISSN: 2782-1994 DOI: 10.31618/EESA.2782-1994 ICI Journal Master List 2019 ICV 2019: 64.33 Issue:56, April 2020/
3. M. S. Akhmedova. TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE AND SPEECH COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS IN THE SYSTEM OF CONTINUING EDUCATION. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR) ISSN 2278-4853, impact Factor SJIF 2022:8.179 Vol 11, Issue 11, November 2022
4. M. S. Akhmedova. W A YS OFDEVELOPMENTOFCOMMUNICATIVE AND SPEECH COMPETENCE OFFUTURE TEACHERS OF PRIMARY EDUCATION. International scientific journal of "Science and Innovation" In Volume 2, Issue 6 of International scientific journal of "Science and Innovation" ISSN: 2181-3337, UIF-2022:8.2, SJIF 2023:5.608
5. М.С. Ахмедова. "Роль гигиенического воспитания в формировани гармонично развитого поколения" "Таълим технологиялари" журнали март 2019 йил
6. М. Ахмедова "Бобур ижоди бўйича адабиет фанидан замонавий дарс технологияси" "Таълим технологиялари" журнали 3- сони 2020йил
7. М. Ахмедова. Преподавание языка и литературы 2023 йил 5-сон ISSN 2010-5584.
8. М. Ахмедова. THE ROLE OF FOLK LANGUAGE TOOLS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH COMPETENCIES OF YOUNGER SCHOOLCHILDREN IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING RUSSIAN (NATIVE) LANGUAGE. МУҒАЛЛИМ ҲАМ УЗЛИКСИЗ БИЛИМЛЕНДИРИЎ Илимий-методикалық журнал Нукус. № 2/2 2023 ISSN 2181-7138
9. М. Ахмедова. Уровни языка и методы лингвистического анализа. Роль непрерывного профессионального Развития в образовании в развитии общества,

- Вопросы реализации: цели и задачи Международная научно-практическая конференция 2022 год 10- апреля Узбекистан
10. М. Ахмедова. ПУТИ РАЗВИТИЯ КОММУНИКАТИВНО-РЕЧЕВОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ БУДУЩИХ ПЕДАГОГОВ НАЧАЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ. Нукус халқаро "Янги методикалар: замонавий педагогларнинг касбий ва шахсий ривожланиш гарови" мавзусидаги халқаро илмий-амалий конференцияси 2023 йил 10- мая Узбекистан
 11. М. Ахмедова. Организация словарной работы с детьми дошкольного возраста в развитии языковой компетенции. "Учинчи ренессанс даврида мактабгача таълим ва тарбиянинг роли" Мавзусидаги Республика талабаларнинг Илмий-амалий анжумани Материаллари 2022 йил 11 март Тошкент
 12. М. Ахмедова. Роль народных языковых средств в развитии речевой компетенции младших школьников. "Бошланғич таълимда халқаро тажрибалар: янги авлод дарсликлари, миллий дастур ва рақамли технологиялар интеграцияси Илмий-амалий анжумани Материаллари 2023 йил 19-май Бухоро
 13. М. Ахмедова. Информационные и мультимедийные технологии на уроках русского языка как средство формирования компетенций обучающихся. International scientific and practical conference "Economics, management and digital innovation in education: modern trends and approaches" mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi March 13, 2024
 14. М. Ахмедова. Языковая политика в узбекистане на современном этапе «Влияние междисциплинарной интеграции в цифровой образовательной среде на эффективность образования: международный опыт и перспективы развития» материалы международной научно-практической конференции 15-16 март 2024 г